

**A CASE STUDY ON BHAGANDARA-ANO RECTAL FISTULA TREATED WITH KSHARA
SUTRA**

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ABSTRACT

Ano rectal fistula is a chronic inflammatory condition with a tract opening (internal opening) in the Anal canal at one end and another opening at the perianal surface/skin (external opening). It is challenging due to its high recurrence rate. Probable risk factors include recurrent fissure in Ano, prolong sitting, obesity, excessive hairs in perianal region. Based on its symptoms, it can be correlated with *Bhagandara* in *Ayurveda*. *Acharya Sushruta* has included it under *Ashtamahagada* and as *Dushchikitsya vyadhi* & have explained five types of *Bhagandara* & various treatment modalities like *bheshaja*, *shastra*, *kshara* etc. Here we have taken a case of Ano rectal fistula of a male aged around 43 years is examined in Shalya tantra OPD, diagnosed with *Bhagandara* and treated with *Ksharasutra*, as it is considered as an ideal parasurgical procedure for the treatment of *Bhagandara* due to its *Ksharana*, *lekhana* and *ropana* properties.

KEYWORDS: *Bhagandara*, Ano rectal fistula, *Kshara Sutra*, Fistula-In-Ano, *Ayurveda*.

• **INTRODUCTION**

Bhagandara is a surgical condition affecting Ano-rectal region. The prevalence in men is 12.3 cases and in women is 5.6 cases per 100,000 populations. The male: female ratio is 1.8:1. The mean age of patients is 38.3 years.^[1] *Acharya Sushruta*, the father of surgery has included this disease under *Ashtamahagada*.^[1] Initially, in the *apakvavastha* (Asuppurative stage), it presents as *pidika* (boil) around the *guda*, *basti*, and *bhaga* called as *Pidaka*, & when it gets suppurated, it forms *Bhagandara*.^[2] Although it is not life-threatening, it causes severe discomfort in routine life due to recurrent pus discharge, pain and discomfort. *Acharya Charaka* has described that certain diseases like *Bhagandara*, *Ashmari*, *Gulma*, *Arsha* etc. may require surgical intervention. *Acharya Sushruta* has explained various treatment modalities like *bheshaja*, *shastra* and *anushastra karmas* like *Kshara*, *Agnikarma* & *Jalaukavcharana* in *Bhagandara*.^[3] Among all, *Kshara* due to its *chedana*, *bhedana*, *lekhana*, *darana*, *ropana* &

tridoshahara properties is considered as one among the most important procedures.

Use of *Kshara* in the form of *Ksharasutra* has become popular due to its easy approach, widely acceptance, minimal tissue loss, cost effectivity and low recurrence rate. *Ksharasutra* is a medicated seton prepared using medicinal plants. It induces both chemical & mechanical cutting of tract and allows effective healing. *Acharya Sushruta* has explained *Kshara sutra* in *Nadi vrana*.^[4] Whereas, *Chakradatta* has described the use of *Kshara sutra* under *Arsha* & *Bhagandara* treatment. The standard *Ksharasutra* is prepared by applying 11 coatings of *Snuhi Ksheera*, followed by 7 coatings of *Snuhi Ksheera*+ *Apamarga Kshara* and then 3 coatings of *Snuhi Ksheera* and *Haridra Churna* to a No 20 linen thread. However, it may cause discomfort, post-procedural pain & requires repeated hospital visits for thread changing, hence inconvenient for few patients.

- **CASE REPORT**

- Age - 43 years
- Gender- male
- Occupation- Manager
- Religion – Hindu
- Marital status – Married
- Date of admission -12/02/24
- Date of recovery - 18/02/24

- **CHIEF COMPLAINTS AND DURATION**

Patient complains of pus discharge from the left perianal region since 2 years.

- **ASSOCIATED COMPLAINTS**

Associated with pain and discomfort while sitting.

- **H/O PRESENT ILLNESS**

A male patient aged around 43 years was asymptomatic before 2 years, later he noticed a boil over left perianal region, for which he applied a corn cap, after which he developed intermittent pus discharge and mild pain around the perianal region. He took Homeopathic treatment for 1.5 years (details of which are not known) and got relief from symptoms for few months. Later the symptoms got aggravated from last 1 month, for which he consulted Apollo hospital where he was advised for Fistulectomy. Patient denied the procedure and approached SDMAH Bangalore, for further management.

- **FAMILY HISTORY**

- Patient is not a known case of DM/HTN/Thyroid dysfunction.
- History of IBS- 2years ago- got cured by Homeopathic treatment.
- Ganglion cyst removal on left wrist- twice- 2004 and 2008.
- Surgery for ACL tear of left knee joint- 2022

- **TREATMENT HISTORY**

Patient used to take Homeopathic medicine for Fistula in Ano and IBS.

- **HISTORY OF ALLERGY**

No known drug or food allergies.

- **PESONAL HISTORY**

- *Ahara* – Mixed- Non-veg 3 times/week, spicy food, frequent intake of junk food(burgers, pizza).
- *Vihara* – Prolong sitting and frequent travelling.
- *Vyasana* – Coffee 2 times/day, Alcohol-occasionally.
- *Jataragni* – *Vishama*.
- *Nidra* – *Prakruta*- 6 hours daily.
- *Bala* – *Madhyama*.

- **FAMILY HISTORY**

Nothing significant.

- **ASTAVIDHA PARIKSHA**

- *Nadi* – *Vata pitta*.
- *Shabda* - *Prakruta*
- *Mala* – Hard stools- once/day.
- *Sparsh* - *Anushna sheeta*.
- *Mutra* - *Prakruta* 4-6 times a day.
- *Drik* - *Prakruta*
- *Jihwa* - *Alipta*
- *Akriti* - *Madhyama*

- **GENERAL EXAMINATION**

- Built : Moderate
- Nourishment : Well nourished.
- Temperature : Afebrile
- Respiratory rate : 18cpm
- Weight : 68kg
- BP : 130/90mmHg
- Pulse : Regular, 86bpm
- Palor : Absent
- Icterus : Absent
- Clubbing : Absent
- Cynosis : Absent
- Edema : Absent
- Lymphadenopathy : Absent

- **SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION**

- CNS : Conscious, Oriented to time, place and person.
- CVS : S₁S₂ heard, No murmurs.
- RS : B/L Normal vesicular breath sound heard.
- GIT: P/A- Soft, non-tender, bowel sounds present, inverted Umbilicus.

- **LOCAL EXAMINATION**

- ✓ ***Darshana/Inspection: Left Peri-anal region.***
- External opening – present at 5 o'clock position-in left perianal region.
- Distance-1.5cm from the anal verge.
- No of opening-1
- No of tract-1
- Pus – Purulent discharge with foul smell.
- Colour of pus- Yellowish.
- Induration-Present.
- Pigmentation-around the opening- present
- Bleeding- Absent.
- External anal mass, skin tags, fissure, abscess, ulcers – Absent.

- ✓ ***Sparshana/Palpation***

- Tenderness- ++
- Temperature- Not raised
- Induration around the tract- Present.

- ✓ ***Digital rectal examination***

- Sphincter tone- Hypertonic
- Rectal lumps/masses/fissure bed – not felt
- Indentation felt at left side- @ 5 o'clock position.
- Blood/mucus discharge- Absent from anal canal.
- Prostate- felt symmetrical and normal in shape, non tender.

✓ **Proctoscopic Examination**

- Rectal mucosa- Non inflamed.
- No fissure/internal pile mass/abscess/ulcer noticed.

✓ **Examination with Probe**

- Tenderness-++

- Pus discharge-+
- Internal opening- @ 5o'clock position
- No of tract- 1
- Tract length- around 1.5cm.

• **LABORATORY INVESTIGATIONS**

Hb- 14gms%
 ESR- 18mm/hr
 RBS- 125mg/dL
 CBC- Within normal limits.
 HIV- Negative
 HbSAg- Negative

• DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

Diagnosis	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<i>Vidrathi</i>	<i>Puya srava</i> and <i>shoola</i> .	Presence of external opening and <i>guda darana</i> .
<i>Shataponaka/Vataja bhagandara</i>	Presence of <i>pidaka</i> in <i>guda pradasha</i> and <i>puya srava</i>	Absence of <i>daruna ruja</i> , <i>aruna phena srava</i> , <i>aneka vrana</i> .
<i>Ushtragreeva/Pittaja</i>	Presence of <i>pidaka</i> in <i>guda pradasha</i> . <i>Ashupaki</i> , <i>ushna</i> and <i>puti srava</i> .	
<i>Parisravi/Kaphaja</i>	Presence of <i>pidaka</i> in <i>guda pradasha</i> .	<i>Kandu</i> , <i>ghana srava</i> , <i>kathina</i> , <i>shweta avabhasa</i> .
<i>Shambukavarta/sannipataja</i>	<i>Srava</i> and pain in <i>guda</i> .	<i>Bahuvarna srava</i> , <i>bahu ruja</i> , <i>shambuka avarta iva</i> .

Diagnosis	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Haemorrhoids	Pain and discomfort in anal region	Absence of mass per anum/rectum.
Perianal abscess	Pus discharge from anal region.	Presence of external opening and tract during examination
Ano rectal fistula	History of boil in anal region and pus discharge. Presence of external opening and tract during examination	
Hidradenitis suppurativa	H/O painful lump in perianal region	No H/O recurrent abscess in anal region or any other body part. Presence of external opening.

• FINAL DIAGNOSIS

- *Pittaja Bhagandara*.
- Anorectal fistula.
- ICD No. – K60. 5

• NIDANA PANCHAKA

- **Nidana:** *Ati katu ahara*, sitting for longer duration, increase travelling, *pittaja ahara*, *asampurna/mithya upachara* of *grahani dosha*.
- **Purvarupa:** Formation of *pidaka*, *shopha* in *guda pradasha*, *pipasa*, *amlodgara*.
- **Rupa:** *Puti puya srava*, presence of external opening.
- **Upashaya:** relieved on lying down in right lateral position.

- **Anupashaya:** aggravated after taking spicy food and traveling.

• SAMPRAPTI GHATAKA

<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Pitta pradhana tridosha</i>
<i>Dushya</i>	<i>Twak Rakta Mamsa</i>
<i>Udbhava sthana</i>	<i>Grahani</i>
<i>Sanchara sthana</i>	<i>Koshta</i>
<i>Vyakta sthana</i>	<i>Guda</i>
<i>Roga Marga</i>	<i>Abhyantara</i>
<i>Srotas</i>	<i>Rasa, rakta, mamsa and purishavaha</i>
<i>Sroto Dushti</i>	<i>Sangha</i>
<i>Sadhya Asadhyata</i>	<i>Kruchra Sadhya/ shastra</i>

Shat kriya Kala:

- **TREATMENT**

- **Surgical Treatment:** DOS: 13/02/24
- **Procedure:** Primary threading under LA
- **Pre-operative**
 - ✓ Informed written consent taken.
 - ✓ Part preparation.
 - ✓ Inj Xylocaine 2% - 0.2ml ID test dose
 - ✓ Inj TT 0.5ml IM stat.
 - ✓ Inj Taxim 1gm IV stat- after test dose.
 - ✓ IVF 1 pint DNS @ 100ml/hr.
 - ✓ Monitor vitals.
- **Operative**
 - ✓ Pt was made to lie in lithotomy position.
 - ✓ Under aseptic precautions part painted and draped.
 - ✓ External opening identified at 5 o'clock position.
 - ✓ Inj Xylocaine 2% infiltration done around the tract.
 - ✓ Probe introduced into the tract to identify internal opening.
 - ✓ Barber's thread tied to the tract.
 - ✓ Adequate haemostasis achieved.
 - ✓ Analgesic suppository administered in the anal canal.
 - ✓ Part cleaned and dressing done.
 - ✓ Pt withstood the procedure well.
- **Post-Operative**
 - ✓ T. Taxim O 200 BD- A/F × 3 days
 - ✓ T. Pan 40mg OD- B/F × 3 days
 - ✓ Tab Zerodol SP- BD
 - ✓ *Swadishta virechana churna* 1tsp @ night time A/F
 - ✓ Replace Barber's thread with *Kshara sutra*-14/02/24
 - ✓ Dressing at MOT
 - ✓ Watch for soakage.
 - ✓ Advise soft diet.
 - ✓ Monitor vitals.
- **PROGRESS**
 - Post op Day 1: Barber's thread was replaced with *Kshara sutra*, minimal soakage, pain+++

- Post op Day 2: Dressing done, soakage-min, pain- +
- Post op Day 3: Dressing done, soakage-nil, pain-reduced.
- Post op Day 4: Discharge/bleeding-absent, dressing done, soakage-nil, pain- reduced.

- **DISCHARGE MEDICINE**

- T. *Triphala guggulu* TID A/F
- T. *Gandhaka rasayana* TID A/F- 7days
- *Swadishta virechana churna* 1tsp @ night A/F
- R/w after one week for *kshara sutra* changing.

- **FOLLOW UP AND OUTCOME**

- Regular follow-up advised with weekly *Ksharasutra* changing.
- Changing of thread was followed as per standard rail road method.
- Increased pus discharge was seen- during first 4 weeks.
- Patient complained of moderate pain during first 3 weeks, later relieved gradually.
- Cut through of the tract was seen after 10 weeks with complete diminishing of pus discharge & complete healing of operated site with healthy granulation.
- No complications observed during and after treatment.
- No recurrence observed till one year.

On 13/02/24- Tract length- 1.4cm

On 15/03/24- Tract length-1cm

On 14/04/24- Tract length- <1cm.

Complete cut through of tract on 30/04/24.

Total sittings- 10

• DISCUSSION

Acharya Sushruta has described various treatment modalities for Fistula in Ano viz. *Bheshaja*, *Ksharakarma*, *Agnikarma* and *Shastra Karma*. In contemporary medicine treatments like fistulotomy, fistulectomy, VAAFT, seton placement, mucosal advancement flap, LIFT procedure, autologous fat grafting, OTSC treatment ligation are indicated. These treatments have more recurrence rate and post-operative complications like hemorrhage, pain, delayed healing etc. Para-surgical measures like *Raktamokshana* (Blood-letting), *Kshara Karma* (Chemical cauterization), *Agnikarma* (Thermal cautery), *Ksharasutra* (Alkaline thread) can be employed either alone or in combination. Among all parasurgical procedures, *Kshara sutra* is widely accepted due to following properties:

Minimal trauma and minimum tissue loss as compared to surgical removal, minimal bleeding, can be done under Local anaesthesia, patient can be ambulated soon after procedure, minimal hospital stay, no incontinence/stricture, Cost effective, scar-narrow and fine, low recurrence rate, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial property and due to its alkaline property helps in cutting and healing.^[5]

• CONCLUSION

Due to improper life style & prolong sitting jobs, the incidence of fistula in ano is increasing. The management of these diseases require complete knowledge of Ano-rectal anatomy and pathophysiology. Also diagnosis and plan of treatment is important based on type and severity of disease. *Ksharasutra* keeps the tract patent, allows continuous drainage, curette, cutting and healing without false closure. So, we can conclude that in Ano-rectal fistula, *Ksharasutra* treatment is a better option due to minimum complications & one can resume daily activities earlier.

• DECLARATION OF PATIENT CONSENT

Authors certify that they have obtained patient consent form, where the patient/caregiver has given his/her consent for reporting the case along with the images and other clinical information in the journal. The

patient/caregiver understands that his/her name and initials will not be published and due efforts will be made to conceal his/her identity, but anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

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Nil.

• CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.

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